

COMPUTER SIMULATION OF 3D FORMING PROCESSES OF FABRIC REINFORCED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

When using fabric reinforced plastics as material in products, the local orientation of the yarns of the fabric in the product depend on the shape of the product and on the initial orientation of the fabric. The final orientation of the yarns is of crucial importance for the mechanical properties of the product. With the help of a geometrical simulation the orientation of the yarns can be predicted. During 3D forming of fabric reinforced plastics, buckling of the yarns may appear. Buckling of the yarns leads to a decrease of the mechanical properties of the fabric. The buckling of the yarns cannot be predicted with a geometrical simulation. Therefore a simulation based on finite element analyses was carried out. It shows that compression in the yarns during 3D forming can occur, and that by applying external loads, these critical compression stresses can be eliminated.

Keywords: Composites, draping, fabric, textiles, manufacturing, deformation kinetics, wrinkling, finite element, large displacement, mechanical properties, graphical simulation

1 INTRODUCTION

The success of fibre reinforced plastics in the aerospace industry is depending on whether the production processes will change from hand lay up to automated processes. Especially fabric reinforced thermoplastic products can be formed with automated processes like rubber forming, deep drawing and diaphragm forming. In the development route from concept to product, the design of production tools is of crucial importance for the quality of the product. The simulation of 3D forming processes is a useful aid in this case.

With such a simulation, the detection of difficulties or even impossibilities can be found before the manufacturing of the production tools. Not only information about if and how a product can be found, but also input data necessary for load calculations in finite element programs can be calculated.

Before the discussion of the two simulation programs, the deformation possibilities of fabrics will be discussed. Examples of several simulations will be shown.

2 DEFORMATION OF FABRICS

During the deformation of one layer of an impregnated fabric several 2D modes of deformation can be seen: fibre stretching, fibre straightening, shear slip, shear, buckling. Each mode has a certain relevance to the deforming process.

- Fibre Stretching

Fibre stretching is caused by pulling forces on the yarns. The maximum allowed strain of yarns used in the aerospace industry is less than 1.5%. Since strains of more than 30% can be found during deformation processes, the fibre stretching mode is of no importance for the deformation of fabrics.

- Fibre Straightening

Fibre straightening is also caused by pulling

forces on the yarns. In theory the strain caused by straightening can be more than 10%. However, in reality flat fabrics are used as reinforcement, and although it has more influence than the stretching mode, the straightening mode is also of relative small importance during the deformation of fabrics.

- Shear Slip

Shear slip is caused by pulling forces perpendicular to the yarns. Shear slip occurs at corners and causes the fabric to tear. It is therefore an unwanted deformation mode of fabrics.

- Shear

The shear deformation is caused by pulling forces in the bias direction of the fabric. With this deformation mode strains of 30% can be realised. The shear deformation mode is seen as the most important deformation mode. The shear mode is often called the trellis effect.

- Buckling

The buckling deformation is caused by compression forces in the direction of the yarns. It leads to local wrinkles or even global folds. Buckling decreases the mechanical properties of yarns, and therefore buckling should be prevented during the forming of a product.

Taking all the deformation modes of fabric in account, it is seen that the shear deformation dictates the deformation of fabrics. The shear deformation is limited by the locking angle. At a certain point during the shearing of a fabric, the force necessary to shear the fabric will increase very fast. At this point the fabric

reaches its locking angle. The locking angle is the parameter that dictates the deformation possibilities of a fabric. The smaller the locking angle the better the deformation possibilities of the fabric. When a 3D shape is formed, the fabric will not only shear, but will also bend. Since yarns are bundles of thin fibres, the bending will not give problems during the forming.

3 GEOMETRICAL MODEL OF A DEFORMATION PROCESS.

When a 3D shape is covered with fabric the direction of the yarns differ from place to place. If a strength or stiffness calculation is needed, a finite element program must be used. The local orientation of the yarns must be known in such a program, to get reliable predictions of the behaviour of the product. This orientation can be calculated by the geometrical simulation program.

3.1 Principle Of The Geometrical Simulation

Of the deformation possibilities of fabrics, the shear mode is the most important deformation mode. And if only the shear mode is used the modelling can be seen as a geometrical model (sometimes called a cinematic model). In this case the fabric is a fisherman net, with yarns that have an infinite stiffness and cross-over points that cannot move. Although the deformation of a fabric is limited in

this way, there is still an infinite number of ways to cover a 3D shape with fabric. Limitations for

Figure 1a-1d Several possible coverings of a cone.

obtaining one solution at a time for covering a shape with fabric are therefore necessary. For instance, if a cone is observed, it can be covered in many ways (figure 1).

When looking at a basic square of a flat fabric only one point and two directions have to be known to generate the rest of the square (figure 2). So when in a flat plane one yarn in weft and one yarn in warp is known, there is only one covering possible. If the amount of cross-over points in warp direction is C_{warp} and the amount of cross-over points in weft direction is C_{weft} than the amount of constraints needed for a unique covering is:

$$(C_{warp} - 1) + (C_{weft} - 1)$$

(1) Figure 2 Basic square of fabric

The major problem left in the geometrical model, is the generation of these constraints. Only when the constraints are calculated in the right way the solution of the simulation can be useful. The way the constraints should be calculated is depending on the process used for deforming the fabric.

The first possible generation of the constraints, found in literature Mack[1], Robertson[2], West[3], is the definition of one yarn in the weft and one yarn in the warp direction. When rotationally symmetric shapes are considered the warp and weft yarns are often placed in a plane of symmetry (figure 1a), this will in general give a decent solution. It is however possible to place the warp and weft yarn in a different way on such a shape (figure 1b-1d).

How to put on beforehand one yarn in weft and one yarn in warp direction on a non symmetrical shape is depending on the shape itself. Instead of defining the constraints on beforehand, the constraints are calculated during the draping of the shape. When a partial covered shape is considered, a constraint can be placed at the edge of the so far draped shape (figure 3). In that case only the place and the direction of the constraint needs to be calculated. If the press forming process is considered (figure 4), the highest point on the edge of the fabric so far, is the point that is cooled down, by die contact, the most. It is therefore logical to add a constraint at that place. The direction of the constraint is, when press forming is considered, the same as the direction of the previous constraint. For rotationally symmetric shapes this highest point method, will lead to the same result as the defining of the warp and weft yarn in a

Figure 3 A partial covered cone.

Figure 4 The press forming process

plane of symmetry on forehead. An other possibility to determine the place and direction of a constraint is the use of a sort of minimal energy method. In that case the place at which the constraint is added is not important, as long as it is on the edge (figure 3). A starting direction must be chosen, and with the use of an iteration method based on the minimal energy method, the right direction can be calculated. An indication for the energy needed to change the direction of the yarns in a fabric is the change of the surface area of a row of cells. In figure 5 the area of a previous calculated row of cells is:

Figure 5 Part of fabric

$$b^2 \sin(\alpha_i) \tag{2}$$

The new row of cells has a surface area of:

$$b^2 \sin(\alpha_i + \Delta\alpha_i) \tag{3}$$

The difference of the areas must be minimal and therefore

$$\left| \sum_{i=1}^n (b^2 \sin(\alpha_i) - b^2 \sin(\alpha_i + \Delta\alpha_i)) \right| \tag{4}$$

should be minimal. So

$$\left| \sum_{i=1}^n (\sin(\alpha_i) - \sin(\alpha_i + \Delta\alpha_i)) \right| \tag{5}$$

should be minimal. In this expression there are $(n-1)$ $\Delta\alpha$ terms that cannot be chosen freely. The $\Delta\alpha$'s are not independent since there is only one constraint per row possible. Therefore:

$$\Delta\alpha_i = f_i(\Delta\alpha_k), \quad k \text{ is a fixed value} \tag{6}$$

By changing the $\Delta\alpha_k$ and calculating the surface area, the minimum change in surface area can be found. When applying this iteratively, any shape can be covered with fabric.

When other processes are considered other methods for finding the right constraints of the fabric can be used. The locking angle (the limitation to the shear deformation) can be incorporated in such a method as well.

Since the simulation gives the user the freedom of defining a rather arbitrary shape, the automated calculation of the constraints sometimes fails to work properly. Especially objects as shown in figure 6 show difficulties in draping. In the program that calculates the simulation, an extra option was added. This option gives the user of the program the possibility to tell the program interactive where the constraint should be placed, and what the direction of the constraint should be. In this way the user can guide the fabric, and decide if the product can be covered with a layer of fabric.

Figure 6 A difficult shape to drape with the highest point method

3.2 Examples Of The Geometrical Simulation

A simple non symmetrical shape is a box. When this box is covered with 0-90 degrees fabric (figure 7), problems will be initiated from the corners. By rotating the fabric 45 degrees, these

Figure 7 A simple box, draped in three ways

problems are moved to the edge surrounding the box. When a prestretched fabric (the initial angle between the warp and weft yarns is less than 90 degrees) is used, no difficult areas are left.

With the T-bar shown in figure 8 a similar case is observed. After rotating the fabric the shape can be covered with fabric without any problems.

Figure 8 the T-bar covered in two ways

The box shown in figure 9 is very difficult to drape in a way that the whole box is covered. What ever initial orientation of the fabric was used, very large shear angles, caused by the "nose", always appeared somewhere on the shape. In this case the box cannot be made out of one piece of fabric. One of the ways to solve that problem is to adjust the shape by deleting the "nose" (figure 9).

Figure 9 The box with the problem area, and without the problem

4 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL OF A DEFORMATION PROCESS.

The geometrical simulation of the draping of fabric is very useful for determining the size and orientation of a fabric, and problems related to the fitting of the fabric on the shape. However, such a simulation cannot tell where to expect compression forces, which can occur during a process. Compression forces lead to buckling and indirect to a decrease in mechanical properties. It is therefore useful to know on forehand where compression forces might occur. As soon as these kind of stress calculations must be done, finite element methods are practical to be used.

4.1 Principle Of The Finite Element Simulation

The first action needed for a finite element approach is the modelling of the process. Since press forming is a promising process (figure 4), it was chosen as the process to be modelled. The female mould is used to consolidate the deformed fabric, and not to deform the fabric. For this reason the female mould was not considered in the simulation. The male mould, together with the blank holder does the actual deforming of the fabric. Friction plays an important role in the forming, and cannot be neglected in the simulation program. During the forming process the deformability of the fabric is dominated by the yarns of which it is woven, the matrix does not play an important role. For this reason the resin was not modelled. However, the effect of the resin on the friction can be accounted for, when the friction on the mould and blank holder is varied locally.

Every yarn of the fabric can be modelled as a collection of one dimensional bars (figure 10). The cross-over points of the yarns are the points where the beams are connected to each other. When the possible deformation modes of a fabric are considered fibre stretching, fibre buckling and shear deformation can be included. The shear slip deformation and the fibre straightening are not included, since characteristics of those phenomena are difficult to determine. The 3D forming process is characterized by the large displacement and the small strains of the yarns. The one dimensional bar is therefore a non-linear large displacement element. This element is also used in problems concerning cables (Besseling[4]).

Figure 10 Fabric as a collection of beams

Figure 11 Definition of the bar element

4.1.1 Definition Of The Bar Element

When a beam element with end points X_1 and X_2 and with displacement vectors U_1 and U_2 is observed (figure 11), the strain can be defined by:

$$\epsilon = \frac{l^2 - l_0^2}{2l_0^2} = \frac{(x_2 - x_1)(u_2 - u_1)}{l_0} + \frac{(y_2 - y_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{l_0} + \frac{(z_2 - z_1)(w_2 - w_1)}{l_0} + \frac{(u_2 - u_1)^2}{2l_0^2} + \frac{(v_2 - v_1)^2}{2l_0^2} + \frac{(w_2 - w_1)^2}{2l_0^2} \quad (7)$$

For small ϵ , the often used expression for ϵ can be found:

$$\epsilon = \frac{l^2 - l_0^2}{2l_0^2} = \frac{(l - l_0)(l + l_0)}{2l_0^2} = \frac{\Delta l}{l_0} \left(1 + \frac{\Delta l}{l_0}\right) \approx \frac{\Delta l}{l_0} \quad (8)$$

The geometrically non linear relations between the generalized strain and end point displacements u_1 and u_2 can per definition be written as:

$$\epsilon \equiv D(u_k) \quad (k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, 6)$$

When the derivatives of D with respect to u_i are written as:

$$D_i = \frac{\delta D}{\delta u_i}, D_{ij} = \frac{\delta}{\delta u_j} \left(\frac{\delta D}{\delta u_i} \right) \quad (10)$$

the demand for continuity, written in an increment form, looks like:

$$\Delta \varepsilon = D_k^c \Delta u_k^c + D_l^o \Delta u_l^o \quad (11)$$

In this equation is u^o the prescribed displacement and u^c the not prescribed displacement (f^c is the prescribed force and f^o is the not prescribed force).

The linear elastic behaviour of a beam can be described by:

$$\sigma = S \varepsilon \quad (12)$$

When a beam is in equilibrium the virtual work of deformation is equal to the virtual work of the external forces working on the beam. This can be expressed as:

$$\sigma \delta \varepsilon = f_k \delta u_k \quad (13)$$

with $\delta \varepsilon = D_k \delta u_k$ and arbitrary δu_k it leads to

$$\sigma D_k = f_k \quad (14)$$

with $\Delta \sigma = S \Delta \varepsilon$, (11) and (14) in increment form the next equation can be found.

$$(D_k^c S D_l^c + \sigma D_{kl}^c) \Delta u_l^c = \Delta f_k^c - (D_k^c S D_m^o + \sigma D_{km}^c) \Delta u_m^o \quad (15)$$

Due to the non linear behaviour, expression (15) will not be satisfied in one step in general. By adding the residual stresses of the equilibrium expression the next expression can be found:

$$(D_k^c S D_l^c + \sigma D_{kl}^c) \Delta u_l^c = \Delta f_k^c - (D_k^c S D_m^o + \sigma D_{km}^c) \Delta u_m^o + f_k^c - \sigma D_k^c \quad (16)$$

This expression can be used for determining a solution for a loading step ($\Delta f_k \neq 0, \Delta u^o \neq 0$) as well as for the following iteration steps ($\Delta f_k = 0, \Delta u^o = 0$) in a finite element program.

4.1.2 Method For Solving The Finite Element Equations

By applying a prestressed fabric the non linear part of the stiffness matrix of an element will in general not be zero and therefore the stiffness matrix will be valid. In many finite element programs the stiffness matrix for the whole structure is composed out of the stiffness matrices of all elements. The dimension of the resulting system of equations that has to be solved can be large. If, for example, a fabric consisting out of 60 yarns in weft and warp direction is used in the model, the amount of equations to be solved is more than 10,000 ($60 \times 60 \times 3$). Therefore an other method for solving the finite element equations has been developed. This method solves the equilibrium locally. If a basic cell of fabric (figure 12) is considered, the end points of all the elements connected to the central point are pinned temporarily. By using expression (16), a new position of the central point can be calculated. By moving through the fabric and using a maximum allowed strain error criterion for satisfying the global equilibrium, this method will in general converge to a solution.

Figure 12
Basic cell of fabric

4.2 Examples Of The Finite Element Simulation

With the geometrical simulation the initial orientation and the size of the fabric covering the box (figure 13) can be found. When using a constant friction force on the box and on the blank holder, buckling occurs at the corners of the box (figure 14). The friction on the box is chosen much larger

Figure 13 The box, blank holder and fabric

than the friction on the blank holder, since in reality the upper die of the forming process is in general relative cold. Extra tensile forces need to be applied in reality to get a box without wrinkles. These forces are created by using pins or local pressure during the process. In the simulation, the forces can be created by applying extra friction forces at several nodes (figure 15).

The size of the buckling zone's decreases when extra friction is applied (figure 16).

Figure 14 The compression zone in the corner.

Figure 15 Extra friction forces on the fabric

Figure 16 The decrease of the compression zone

Conclusive Remarks

The calculation methods presented in this paper have been implemented in computer programs for MS-DOS machines. The results do remarkably well fit the produced prototype components up to now. In the future special attention will be given to thickness deviations of the used materials and finite element interfaces (grid definitions, local material properties, etc).

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